

Chemical Investigation on *Limnophila rogusa* and *Pedilanthus tithymaloides*

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In previous communications, we reported the isolation and identification of some flavones from the whole plant (aerial parts and roots) of *Limnophila rogusa*¹ and one triterpene from the whole plant *Pedilanthus tithymaloides*². We now report the isolation and characterisation of some more phytochemicals from this two plants.

Air-dried and powdered whole plant of *L. rogusa* was extracted with benzene. The concentrate of the extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)-benzene (3 : 1) mixture afforded betulin as white needles (ethanol), m.p. 250–51°, $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$ (M^+ 442); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 480 (OH), 1 645 cm^{-1} (C=C); diacetyl derivative, m.p. 216°, $C_{34}H_{54}O_4$ (M^+ 526). Further elution of the column with benzene furnished betulinic acid, m.p. 315–16°, $C_{30}H_{48}O_3$ (M^+ 456); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH), 1 695 (COOH) and 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=C); methyl-ester, m.p. 222–24°, $C_{30}H_{50}O_3$ (M^+ 470); acetyl derivative of methyl ester, m.p. 285–87°, $C_{32}H_{52}O_4$ (M^+ 512).

Air-dried and powdered whole plant of *P. tithymaloides* was extracted successively with petroleum ether and benzene. The concentrated petroleum extract on chromatography over silica gel gave octacosanol as white solid, m.p. 83–84°, ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 350 cm^{-1} (M^+ 410) in petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluate. Further elution of the column with benzene afforded cycloartenone, m.p. 107° (methanol), ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 710 cm^{-1} ; m/z 424 (M^+), 409, 340, 313 and 286; oxime, m.p. 168–70°. The benzene extract on usual chromatographic resolution yielded β -sitosterol. The identity of each of the compounds reported herein has been confirmed by direct comparison with authentic samples³.

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